

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Computational Statistics and Data Analysis

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/csda

Skewness and kurtosis of multivariate Markov-switching processes

Gabriele Fiorentini^{a,b}, Christophe Planas^{c,*}, Alessandro Rossi^c

^a University of Florence, School of Economics, Italy

^b Rimini Centre for Economic Analysis, Italy

^c European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 19 December 2014

Received in revised form 25 June 2015

Accepted 25 June 2015

Available online 10 July 2015

Keywords:

Markov-switching

VAR models

Higher-order moments

State space models

ABSTRACT

Exact formulae are provided for the calculation of multivariate skewness and kurtosis of Markov-switching Vector Auto-Regressive (MS VAR) processes as well as for the general class of MS state space (MS SS) models. The use of the higher-order moments in non-linear modeling is illustrated with two examples. A Matlab code that implements the results is available from the authors.

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1. Introduction

Markov-switching models are now widespread in applied macroeconomics and finance. By extending linear specifications with a discrete latent process that controls parameter switches, MS models have gained the ability to fit time series subject to non-linearities. In macroeconomics, MS models have been introduced by Hamilton (1989) with the aim of capturing the asymmetry of the business cycle. Kim and Nelson (1999a) and Mc Connell and Perez-Quiros (2000) have extended the Hamilton model to account for the reduction in business cycle fluctuations known as the Great Moderation. Phillips (1991) has applied the Hamilton model to a multi-country case. Ang and Bekaert (2002a) have underlined the usefulness of a multivariate dimension when analyzing switches in the dynamics of the US, UK, and German short-term interest rates. Favero and Monacelli (2005) and Sims and Zha (2006) have resorted to the MS VAR framework to detect shifts in the US monetary and fiscal policy. Given the empirical evidence about the existence of policy regimes, the last generation of dynamic stochastic general equilibrium models includes Markov-switching policy reaction functions (see Davig and Leeper, 2007; Davig et al., 2004). In this context MS VAR models arise as fundamental solution of the forward-looking structural equations (Farmer et al., 2009, 2011). MS models have also been intensively used in empirical finance to reproduce the fat tails, leverage effects, volatility clustering, and time-varying correlations that characterize many financial return series. Also in this context switching regimes have been inserted into equilibrium models: Cecchetti et al. (1990, 1993), for instance, have added regimes to the conventional asset pricing model through switching processes for dividends and consumption. General discussions and additional references can be found in Krolzig (1997), Kim and Nelson (1999b), Fruhwirth-Schnatter (2006), Ang and Timmermann (2011), and Guidolin (2012).

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: fiorentini@disia.unifi.it (G. Fiorentini), christophe.planas@jrc.ec.europa.eu (C. Planas), alessandro.rossi@jrc.ec.europa.eu (A. Rossi).

The statistical properties of MS VAR models have been analyzed, among others, by Yang (2000), Francq and Zakoian (2001, 2002), and Cavicchioli (2013, 2014). These studies focus on stationarity issues, on the first two unconditional moments, and on the determination of the number of regimes. Timmermann (2000) derives the first four moments for univariate MS models. In spite of their relevance, the higher-order moments are still unknown in the general multivariate case. We give closed-form formulae for multivariate MS VAR processes as well as for the general class of MS state space models (see Kim, 1993, 1994). In an independent research paper, Cavicchioli (2015) also derives closed-form expressions for the moments of MS VARMA models up to any order and proposes alternative measures of skewness and kurtosis.

The general MS VAR and MS state space models are presented in Section 2. We focus on models where the discrete latent variable takes a finite number of states with time-invariant transition probabilities. In Section 3, we derive formulae for the higher-order moments for both MS VAR and MS SS models. The use of the higher-order moments is illustrated in Section 4 with two examples. Section 5 concludes. All proofs are given as supplementary material (see Appendix A).

2. Model and assumptions

Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{P})$ be a probability space on which a vector process $\{\varepsilon_t\}$ and a K -state Markov chain $\{S_t\}$ are defined at discrete time t . The first-order MS VAR process for the n_x -dimensional vector $\{x_t\}$ is generated by the stochastic difference equation:

$$x_t = \alpha_{S_t} + \Phi_{S_t} x_{t-1} + \Lambda_{S_t} \varepsilon_t. \tag{2.1}$$

Specifications involving more lags can easily be cast into the formulation above through the VAR(1) companion form. The following assumptions are supposed to hold:

- (i) The n_x -dimensional shocks $\{\varepsilon_t\}$ verify $\varepsilon_t \sim iidN(0, I_{n_x})$, where I_{n_x} denotes the $n_x \times n_x$ identity matrix.
- (ii) The Markov chain $\{S_t\}$ is homogeneous, irreducible, aperiodic, and non-null persistent. These conditions ensure stationarity of $\{S_t\}$ (see e.g. Grimmett and Stirzaker, 1992).
- (iii) The processes $\{\varepsilon_t\}$ and $\{S_t\}$ are independent.
- (iv) The $n_x \times 1$ vector α_{S_t} , and the $n_x \times n_x$ matrices Φ_{S_t} and Λ_{S_t} take as many values as the realization of S_t , i.e. $\alpha_{S_t} \in \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_K\}$, $\Phi_{S_t} \in \{\Phi_1, \dots, \Phi_K\}$, and $\Lambda_{S_t} \in \{\Lambda_1, \dots, \Lambda_K\}$.

The variable x_t may be unobserved. In this case it is typically related to a vector of n_y observations y_t through the measurement equation:

$$y_t = a_{S_t} + H_{S_t} x_t + \gamma_{S_t} u_t. \tag{2.2}$$

Eqs. (2.1)–(2.2) make up a MS state space model. The following additional assumptions are made:

- (v) The n_u -dimensional process $\{u_t\}$ is such that $u_t \sim iidN(0, I_{n_u})$.
- (vi) The process $\{u_t\}$ is independent of $\{\varepsilon_t\}$ and $\{S_t\}$.
- (vii) The $n_y \times 1$ vector a_{S_t} , the $n_y \times n_x$ matrix H_{S_t} , and the $n_y \times n_u$ matrix γ_{S_t} take K different values depending on the realization of the discrete latent variable S_t .

Throughout the paper, we denote p_{jk} the conditional probability $p_{jk} = \mathcal{P}(S_t = k | S_{t-1} = j)$ for $j, k = 1, \dots, K$, π_k the marginal probability of state k , i.e. $\pi_k = \mathcal{P}(S_t = k)$, and π the $K \times K$ matrix with (π_1, \dots, π_K) on the main diagonal and zeros elsewhere. We call $J_{n,k}$ the $n \times nK$ matrix $J_{n,k} = [0_{n \times n(k-1)}, I_n, 0_{n \times n(K-k)}]$, $k = 1, \dots, K$; all together the K matrices $J_{n,k}$ sum to $J_n = \sum_{k=1}^K J_{n,k}$. For any two $n \times 1$ vectors A and B we denote R_n the $n^2 \times n^2$ commutation matrix such that $A \otimes B = R_n(B \otimes A)$. This commutation matrix can be built as $R_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n (e_i e_j') \otimes (e_j e_i')$, e_j being the $n \times 1$ canonical vector $e_j = [0'_{j-1}, 1, 0'_{n-j}]'$ (see Magnus and Neudecker, 1999). For any integer m , we also define $P_m(\Phi)$ the $Kn_x^m \times Kn_x^m$ matrix such that:

$$P_m(\Phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \overbrace{\Phi_1 \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_1}^{m \text{ times}} p_{11} & \Phi_1 \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_1 p_{21} & \dots & \Phi_1 \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_1 p_{K1} \\ \Phi_2 \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_2 p_{12} & \Phi_2 \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_2 p_{22} & \dots & \Phi_2 \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_2 p_{K2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \Phi_K \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_K p_{1K} & \Phi_K \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_K p_{2K} & \dots & \Phi_K \otimes \dots \otimes \Phi_K p_{KK} \end{pmatrix}. \tag{2.3}$$

Finally we denote $\rho(M)$ the spectral radius of matrix M .

3. Multivariate measures of skewness and kurtosis

In macroeconomics and finance, non-linearities are typically analyzed through pairwise measures of skewness and kurtosis such as:

$$\frac{Cov(w_{it}^k, w_{jt}^\ell)}{V(w_{it})^{k/2} V(w_{jt})^{\ell/2}} \tag{3.1}$$

where w_{it} and w_{jt} are two scalar elements of a n -dimensional random vector w_t with finite moments, V and Cov stand for variance and covariance respectively, and k, ℓ are strictly positive integers whose sum $k + \ell = 3, 4$ gives the moment order. The case $i = j$ yields the univariate higher order moments and $i \neq j$ the mixed-moments. All moments given by (3.1) can be

collected into the $n^3 \times 1$ and $n^4 \times 1$ vectors:

$$Sk(w_t; \Sigma_w) = E[\Sigma_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t)) \otimes \Sigma_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t)) \otimes \Sigma_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t))] \\ Ku(w_t; \Sigma_w) = E[\Sigma_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t)) \otimes \Sigma_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t)) \otimes \Sigma_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t)) \otimes \Sigma_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t))] \quad (3.2)$$

where E is the expectation and Σ_w is variance–covariance matrix of w_t with zeros outside the main diagonal, i.e. $\Sigma_w = \text{diag}[V(w_t)]$.

Mardia (1970) proposed alternative definitions of multivariate skewness and kurtosis known as $\beta_{1,n}$ and $\beta_{2,n}$ which aggregate univariate and mix-moments. As shown in Kollo and Srivastava (2005) and Kollo (2008), Mardia’s statistics can be easily retrieved from (3.2) since:

$$\beta_{1,n} = \text{tr}\{E[w_t^* \otimes w_t^{*'} \otimes w_t^*]E[w_t^* \otimes w_t^{*'} \otimes w_t^*]\} = Sk(w_t; \Lambda_w)'Sk(w_t; \Lambda_w) \\ \beta_{2,n} = \text{tr}\{E[w_t^* w_t^{*'} \otimes w_t^* w_t^{*'}]\} = \text{Vec}(I_{n^2})'Ku(w_t; \Lambda_w)$$

where tr represents trace, w_t^* is such that $w_t^* = \Lambda_w^{-1/2}(w_t - E(w_t))$, and Λ_w is any symmetric square root of $V(w_t)$. Other measures of skewness and kurtosis can be found in the literature, for instance in Mori et al. (1993); they can be similarly calculated using formula (3.2). Without loss of generality we focus on the measures of skewness and kurtosis given in (3.2).

3.1. Markov-switching vector autoregressive models

Given the MS VAR process $\{x_t\}$ in (2.1) with assumptions (i)–(iv), let us define z_t the standardized variable $z_t = \Sigma_x^{-1/2}(x_t - E(x_t))$ where $\Sigma_x = \text{diag}[V(x_t)]$. By construction $Sk(x_t; \Sigma_x) = E(z_t \otimes z_t \otimes z_t)$ and $Ku(x_t; \Sigma_x) = E(z_t \otimes z_t \otimes z_t \otimes z_t)$. It is easily checked that $\{z_t\}$ follows the MS VAR process:

$$z_t = c_{S_t} + \Psi_{S_t} z_{t-1} + \Omega_{S_t} \varepsilon_t \\ c_{S_t} = \Sigma_x^{-1/2}(\alpha_{S_t} - E(x_t) + \Phi_{S_t} E(x_t)) \\ \Psi_{S_t} = \Sigma_x^{-1/2} \Phi_{S_t} \Sigma_x^{1/2} \\ \Omega_{S_t} = \Sigma_x^{-1/2} \Lambda_{S_t}. \quad (3.3)$$

Theorem 1 uses the auxiliary process $\{z_t\}$ for deriving the skewness and kurtosis for the general MS VAR process (2.1).

Theorem 1. Suppose $\{x_t\}$ follows the process (2.1) and that $\rho(P_m(\Phi)) < 1$ for $m \leq 4$. Then:

(I) the skewness of the vector x_t is given by

$$Sk(x_t; \Sigma_x) = J_{n_x^3}[I_{Kn_x^3} - P_3(\Psi)]^{-1}D \quad (3.4)$$

where D is the $Kn_x^3 \times 1$ vector $D = (\pi_1 d_1, \pi_2 d_2, \dots, \pi_K d_K)'$ whose $n_x^3 \times 1$ elements d_k are equal to:

$$d_k = c_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k + A_3 \left\{ (\Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes c_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_x}) \right. \\ \left. + [c_k \otimes c_k + (\Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_x})] \otimes \left\{ \Psi_k \sum_{j=1}^K p_{jk} \frac{\pi_j}{\pi_k} \Sigma_x^{-1/2} [E(x_t | S_t = j) - E(x_t)] \right\} \right. \\ \left. + (\Psi_k \otimes \Psi_k \otimes c_k) \sum_{j=1}^K p_{jk} \frac{\pi_j}{\pi_k} (\Sigma_x^{-1/2} \otimes \Sigma_x^{-1/2}) \right. \\ \left. \times [E(x_t \otimes x_t | S_t = j) - E(x_t | S_t = j) \otimes E(x_t) - E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t | S_t = j) + E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t)] \right\},$$

c_k , Ψ_k and Ω_k are defined in (3.3), the $Kn_x^3 \times Kn_x^3$ matrix $P_3(\Psi)$ is like in (2.3), $\Sigma_x = \text{diag}[V(x_t)]$, and the $n_x^3 \times n_x^3$ matrix A_3 is given below:

$$A_3 = I_{n_x^3} + (I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x}) + (R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x})(I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x}), \quad (3.5)$$

(II) the kurtosis of the vector x_t is given by

$$Ku(x_t; \Sigma_x) = J_{n_x^4}[I_{Kn_x^4} - P_4(\Psi)]^{-1}M \quad (3.6)$$

where $P_4(\Psi)$ is like in (2.3), M is the $Kn_x^4 \times 1$ vector $M = (\pi_1 m_1, \pi_2 m_2, \dots, \pi_K m_K)'$ whose $n_x^4 \times 1$ elements m_k are equal to:

$$m_k = c_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k + A_4(c_k \otimes c_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_x}) + (\Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k)B \\ + \tilde{A}_4 \left\{ [c_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k + A_3(\Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes c_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_x})] \otimes \left(\Psi_k \sum_{j=1}^K p_{jk} \frac{\pi_j}{\pi_k} \Sigma_x^{-1/2} [E(x_t | S_t = j) - E(x_t)] \right) \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ A_4[\Psi_k \otimes \Psi_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k + (\Psi_k \otimes \Psi_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_x})] \sum_{j=1}^K p_{jk} \frac{\pi_j}{\pi_k} (\Sigma_x^{-1/2} \otimes \Sigma_x^{-1/2}) \\
 &\times [E(x_t \otimes x_t | S_t = j) - E(x_t | S_t = j) \otimes E(x_t) - E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t | S_t = j) + E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t)] \\
 &+ \tilde{A}_4(\Psi_k \otimes \Psi_k \otimes \Psi_k \otimes c_k) \sum_{j=1}^K \frac{p_{jk}}{\pi_k} J_{n_x^3, j} [I_{Kn_x^3} - P_3(\Psi)]^{-1} D,
 \end{aligned}$$

where the matrix D is detailed in (1) above, the $n_x^4 \times n_x^4$ matrix A_4 and the n_x^4 -dimensional vector B verify:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_4 = & I_{n_x^4} + (I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x}) + (R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x^2})(I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x}) \\
 & + (I_{n_x^2} \otimes R_{n_x})(I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x}) + (I_{n_x^2} \otimes R_{n_x})(R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x^2})(I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x}) \\
 & + (I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x})(I_{n_x^2} \otimes R_{n_x})(R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x^2})(I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x})
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

$$B = \text{Vec}(I_{n_x^2} + R_{n_x}) + \text{Vec}(I_{n_x}) \otimes \text{Vec}(I_{n_x}) \tag{3.8}$$

and the $n_x^4 \times n_x^4$ matrix \tilde{A}_4 is such as

$$\tilde{A}_4 = I_{n_x^4} + (I_{n_x^2} \otimes R_{n_x}) + (I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x})(I_{n_x^2} \otimes R_{n_x}) + (R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x^2})(I_{n_x} \otimes R_{n_x} \otimes I_{n_x})(I_{n_x^2} \otimes R_{n_x}). \tag{3.9}$$

Proof. See [Appendix A](#).

The conditional moments $E(x_t | S_t = j)$ and $E(x_t \otimes x_t | S_t = j)$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, K$, are given in Lemma 1 in [Appendix A](#). It is easily checked that the relationship $\Psi_{S_t} = \Sigma_x^{-1/2} \Phi_{S_t} \Sigma_x^{1/2}$ and the assumptions $\rho(P_3(\Phi)) < 1$ and $\rho(P_4(\Phi)) < 1$ imply invertibility of the matrices $I_{Kn_x^3} - P_3(\Psi)$ and $I_{Kn_x^4} - P_4(\Psi)$ in Eqs. (3.4) and (3.6).

In the absence of the autoregressive lag, i.e. when $\Phi_{S_t} = 0$, model (2.1) is Gaussian conditionally to the concurrent state S_t so the distribution of x_t is a finite mixture of normal densities (see for example [Fiorentini et al., 2014](#)). In empirical finance the efficient market hypothesis provides a compelling argument for excluding autoregressive terms, so the finite mixture model has often been applied to the analysis of returns, for instance by [Ang and Bekaert \(2002b\)](#) and [Taamouti \(2012\)](#). [Theorem 1](#) simplifies as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Sk(x_t; \Sigma_x) &= \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \{c_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k + A_3(\Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes c_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_x})\} \\
 Ku(x_t; \Sigma_x) &= \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \{c_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k \otimes c_k + A_4(c_k \otimes c_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_x}) + (\Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k \otimes \Omega_k) B\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

We turn to the moments of MS SS process.

3.2. Markov-switching state space models

The first two unconditional moments of vector y_t in (2.1)–(2.2) are easily derived from the state conditional moments $E(x_t | S_t)$ and $E(x_t \otimes x_t | S_t)$ since:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(y_t) &= \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k [a_k + H_k E(x_t | S_t = k)] \\
 \text{Vec}[V(y_t)] &= \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k [a_k \otimes a_k + H_k \otimes H_k E(x_t \otimes x_t | S_t = k) + (\gamma_k \otimes \gamma_k) \text{Vec}(I_{n_u}) \\
 &\quad + (a_k \otimes H_k + H_k \otimes a_k) E(x_t | S_t = k)] - E(y_t) \otimes E(y_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.11}$$

Like for the MS VAR case, we define y_t^* the standardized variable $y_t^* = \Sigma_y^{-1/2}(y_t - E(y_t))$ where $\Sigma_y = \text{diag}[V(y_t)]$. Again, this standardization simplifies algebra since $Sk(y_t; \Sigma_y) = E(y_t^* \otimes y_t^* \otimes y_t^*)$ and $Ku(y_t; \Sigma_y) = E(y_t^* \otimes y_t^* \otimes y_t^* \otimes y_t^*)$. It is easily checked that $\{y_t^*\}$ follows the process:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_t^* &= a_{S_t}^* + H_{S_t}^* z_t + \gamma_{S_t}^* u_t \\
 a_{S_t}^* &= \Sigma_y^{-1/2}(a_{S_t} - E(y_t) + H_{S_t} E(x_t)) \\
 H_{S_t}^* &= \Sigma_y^{-1/2} H_{S_t} \Sigma_x^{1/2} \\
 \gamma_{S_t}^* &= \Sigma_y^{-1/2} \gamma_{S_t}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

where z_t and Σ_x are defined in Section 3.1. [Theorem 2](#) provides the skewness and kurtosis of MS SS processes.

Theorem 2. Suppose $\{y_t\}$ evolves as in (2.1)–(2.2) and that $\rho(P_m(\Phi)) < 1$ for $m \leq 4$. Then:

(I) the skewness of the vector y_t is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 Sk(y_t; \Sigma_y) = & \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \{ a_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes a_k^* + A_3^* [(\gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \otimes a_k^*) \text{Vec}(I_{n_u}) \\
 & + (a_k^* \otimes a_k^* + \gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \text{Vec}(I_{n_u})) \otimes (H_k^* \Sigma_x^{-1/2} [E(x_t|S_t = k) - E(x_t)]) \\
 & + H_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes a_k^* (\Sigma_x^{-1/2} \otimes \Sigma_x^{-1/2}) \times (E(x_t \otimes x_t|S_t = k) - E(x_t|S_t = k) \otimes E(x_t) \\
 & - E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t|S_t = k) + E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t))] \} + (H_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes H_k^*) J_{n_x^3, k} [I_{Kn_x^3} - P_3(\Psi)]^{-1} D \quad (3.13)
 \end{aligned}$$

where a_k^* , H_k^* , and γ_k^* are shown in (3.12), the $n_y^3 \times n_y^3$ matrix A_3^* is like in (3.5) with dimension n_y instead of n_x , $\Sigma_x = \text{diag}[V(x_t)]$, and D is detailed in Theorem 1.

(II) the kurtosis of the vector y_t is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ku(y_t; \Sigma_y) = & \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \{ a_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes a_k^* + A_4^* (a_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^*) \text{Vec}(I_{n_u}) + (\gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^*) B^* \\
 & + \tilde{A}_4^* (a_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes H_k^*) \Sigma_x^{-1/2} [E(x_t|S_t = k) - E(x_t)] \\
 & + A_4^* (a_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* + H_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^*) [\Sigma_x^{-1/2} [E(x_t|S_t = k) - E(x_t)] \otimes \text{Vec}(I_{n_u})] \\
 & + A_4^* (a_k^* \otimes a_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes H_k^*) \\
 & \times (\Sigma_x^{-1/2} \otimes \Sigma_x^{-1/2}) [E(x_t \otimes x_t|S_t = k) - E(x_t|S_t = k) \otimes E(x_t) - E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t|S_t = k) \\
 & + E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t)] + A_4^* (H_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^* \otimes \gamma_k^*) \\
 & \times [\text{Vec}(I_{n_u}) \otimes (\Sigma_x^{-1/2} \otimes \Sigma_x^{-1/2}) [E(x_t \otimes x_t|S_t = k) - E(x_t|S_t = k) \otimes E(x_t) \\
 & - E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t|S_t = k) + E(x_t) \otimes E(x_t)]] \} \\
 & + \tilde{A}_4^* (H_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes a_k^*) J_{n_x^3, k} [I_{Kn_x^3} - P_3(\Psi)]^{-1} D \\
 & + (H_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes H_k^* \otimes H_k^*) J_{n_x^4, k} [I_{Kn_x^4} - P_4(\Psi)]^{-1} M \quad (3.14)
 \end{aligned}$$

where M is detailed in Theorem 1, the $n_y^4 \times n_y^4$ matrices A_4^* and \tilde{A}_4^* are like in (3.7) and (3.9) with dimension n_y instead of n_x , and the $n_u^4 \times 1$ vector B^* is like in (3.8) with dimension n_u instead of n_x .

The proof is omitted as it follows closely that of Theorem 1 when $\Phi_{S_t} = 0$, the measurement Eq. (2.2) not involving autoregressive lags. It makes use of the higher-order moments of the state variable x_t which are known. Two examples below illustrate the use of the higher-order moments in multivariate MS models.

4. Examples

UK asset returns

Guidolin and Timmermann (2005, GT) fit a MS VAR model to the UK stock and bond monthly excess returns for the period 1976–2 to 2000–12. They consider three regimes that impact the intercept, the autoregressive matrix, and the shocks variance–covariance matrix. The regimes are interpreted as bear, normal, and bull market periods. Table 1 shows the model-based skewness and kurtosis of the UK stock and bond excess returns as implied by the parameter values given in GT’s Table 4. The co-skewness statistics reported in Table 1 relates the level of the first variable to the square of the second one, whereas the co-kurtosis relates the level of the first variable to the cube of the second variable. In order to gauge the model fit, the empirical counterparts are also displayed together with the 95% confidence intervals computed using the block bootstrap proposed by Politis and Romano (1994). The empirical excess kurtosis are significantly greater than zero, justifying the use of a non-linear model for describing UK stock and bond returns. The two univariate model-based kurtosis confirms that the model correctly weights extreme returns on the two assets. The sample skewness of stocks is significantly negative while no asymmetry is detected in the distribution of bond returns. The model adequately captures these features. The empirical co-skewness of stock and bond returns are almost null, suggesting that the level of each variable is not impacted by the volatility of the other one. The model catches this feature also remarkably well. With a value equal to 2.05, the empirical co-kurtosis of stock returns suggests that extreme values of bond returns have some impact on average stock returns. Conversely, the empirical co-kurtosis of bond returns is almost null: extreme values of stock returns have no impact on bond returns on average. With a value equal to 3.15, the model-based co-kurtosis of bonds falls outside the empirical confidence interval, so the model leads to the unsupported conclusion that bonds cannot diversify the risk inherent to a portfolio of stocks.

US business cycle

Chauvet (1998) and Kim and Nelson (1998) consider a MS dynamic factor model to extract a composite index of the US business cycle out of the growth rates of four US macroeconomic series, namely industrial production, non-farm payroll

Table 1
Higher-order moments of UK stock and bond excess returns.

	Skewness	Kurtosis	Co-skewness	Co-kurtosis
Stocks				
Empirical	−1.17 (−2.12, −0.06)	8.68 (3.21, 13.37)	0.11 (−0.20, 0.40)	2.05 (0.90, 3.10)
Model-based	−0.53	6.92	−0.02	2.65
Bonds				
Empirical	0.55 (−0.30, 1.34)	6.08 (3.09, 8.88)	0.15 (−0.28, 0.55)	−0.02 (−2.71, 2.30)
Model-based	−0.18	5.08	−0.05	3.15

Notes: the model-based moments have been calculated using the parameter estimates given in Table 4 of GT (2005); the co-skewness relates the level of the variable of interest to the square of the other one; the co-kurtosis relates the level of the variable of interest to the cube of the other variable; 95% confidence intervals are reported between parenthesis.

Table 2
Higher-order moments of US industrial production and employment.

	IP		EM		EM - IP	
	Skewness	Kurtosis	Skewness	Kurtosis	Co-skewness	Co-kurtosis
Empirical						
	−0.93 (−1.48, −0.06)	6.99 (4.13, 9.17)	−0.43 (−1.01, 0.23)	5.05 (3.65, 7.14)	−0.69 (−1.10, −0.14)	3.57 (2.34, 5.21)
Model-based						
M_0	−0.31	3.24	−0.10	3.05	−0.22	1.62
M_1	−0.08	4.15	−0.06	3.79	−0.07	2.53

Notes: IP refers to the US Industrial Production Index and EM to the US non-farm employment; co-skewness refers to the third-moment that involves employment and the square of Industrial Production; the co-kurtosis statistics relates the square of the two variables; M_0 : model with switching growth; M_1 : model with switches in growth and in volatility; 95% confidence intervals are reported between parenthesis.

employment, personal income less transfer payments, and real manufacturing and trade sales. The dynamic factor model is specified as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_0 : y_{it} &= \lambda_i f_t + v_{it} \\
 v_{it} &= \phi_{i1} v_{it-1} + \phi_{i2} v_{it-2} + \sigma_i \epsilon_{it} \\
 f_t &= \mu_{S_{1t}} + a_t
 \end{aligned}$$

where a_t and ϵ_{it} , $i = 1, \dots, 4$, are standard Gaussian white noises. The mean of the common factor f_t switches between two values μ_1, μ_2 , according to the phase of the business cycle which is indexed by the discrete latent variable $S_{1t} \in \{1, 2\}$. Camacho et al. (CPP, 2012), estimate model M_0 on US monthly observations from January 1967 to November 2010.

Table 2 shows both empirical and model-based moments of the growth rate of Industrial Production and Employment. For the two variables the empirical skewness is negative as well as the co-skewness. The model adequately reproduces these features. The two series exhibit an excess kurtosis which is sizeable and significant. Model M_0 however implies almost zero excess kurtosis. Table 2 also shows the co-kurtosis statistics which relates the square of the two variables. Its empirical value is equal to 3.57 with confidence interval (2.34, 5.21). Since the theoretical value under normality equals 1.37, this reveals the presence of excess co-movements in volatility between Employment and Industrial Production in the US. Model M_0 however does not foresee this feature as it implies a co-kurtosis of 1.62, outside of the confidence interval. To catch this non-linearity, we allow for heteroskedasticity in the common shock a_t as in:

$$M_1 : f_t = \mu_{S_{1t}} + \sigma_{S_{2t}} a_t.$$

The variance of $\sigma_{S_{2t}} a_t$ now switches between two regimes according to the two-state Markov-variable S_{2t} which is independent of S_{1t} . We estimate model M_1 by approximated maximum likelihood (Kim, 1994). The higher-order moments under M_1 are displayed in the last row of Table 2. Model M_1 yields third and fourth moments that lie inside the empirical 95% confidence intervals. Hence modeling co-movements in volatility improves the characterization of US Employment and Industrial Production compared to the original CPP's specification.

5. Conclusion

We extend the early work by Timmermann (2000) on univariate MS models by deriving closed-form formulae for the multivariate skewness and kurtosis in both MS VAR and MS state space models. Besides enriching the model interpretation by summarizing non-linear features, these formulae provide a useful tool for diagnostic checking via moment-matching. A Matlab code that implements the results in the paper is available from the authors.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to Dante Amengual, Gaby Perez-Quiros and Enrique Sentana as well as audiences at CEMFI Madrid, JRC Ispra, RCEF 2014 Rimini, and ESEM 2014 Toulouse for their comments and suggestions. Special thanks are due to Massimo Guidolin for very helpful discussions. We also thank the Associate Editor and two anonymous referees for useful comments that have greatly help us improving the paper. Of course, the usual caveat applies. Fiorentini acknowledges funding from MIUR PRIN MISURA – Multivariate models for risk assessment.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

The proof of [Theorem 1](#) is given in the Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2015.06.009>.

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